

GRANULAR-MEDIUM-BASED ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY:

Effectiveness and efficiency of automotive bumpers, and other impact-guards depends primarily on properties of materials, and mode(s) of impact energy absorption and/or dissipation. A granular-medium-based impact energy management system was previously proposed, capitalizing on granular dissipative mechanics. This paper focuses on predictive mathematical modeling of its critical design factors.

Keywords: *Granular media, impact energy, automotive bumpers*

INTRODUCTION

Glass generally has a low impact or crash strength. Previous experimental drop-weight tests conducted cyclically on the system from a height of 0.3m (2, 43 m/s or 8, 73 km/h) showed no breakage of the system's glass beads, the core energy dissipating material [1]. This is more than the statutorily stipulated FMVSS velocity of 8km/h for automotive bumper systems. This deviation from material's strength design focus, to dissipation dynamics may be optimized through analytical review of the systems behavior. This may be woven around iterative variation of the system's parameters and loading conditions. In light of the numerous possible design applications, this would vet to many of the disadvantages of experimental testing procedures. As an effort to circumvent this, an mathematical model has been developed as a helpful design tool.

The system has been broken down into four main components; the *skin*, *encapsulating-membrane*, *granular media*, and *base plate*. Each one of them absorbs/dissipates impact energy through one or more mechanisms. Factors affecting the efficiency of each component in the global context of the system have been investigated and considered in the mathematical modeling process.

MATHEMATICAL MODELING

For the purposes of the modeling process, Figure 1 shows a conceptual assembly of the four main components of the system. Across the system's cross-section, none of the components is bonded to the other, including the granular media. Notably, at any point of impact incidence that may be considered, the system's components may be considered

(and analyzed) to constitute a *non-bonded sandwich panel*, with different impact energy absorption and/or dissipation mechanics as illustrated in detailed Figure 2:

Figure 1: Sketch of longitudinal cross-sectional view of the system.

Figure 2: Scheme of energy absorption / dissipation components

By applying the *energy balance approach*, total impact energy absorbed and/or dissipated by the system, E_T , will be given by:

$$E_T = \sum_{i=1}^{10} E_i \quad (1)$$

where E_i = energy absorbed / dissipated by components A, B, C, and D in different modes.

Each mode is unique to the properties of the constituent material as well as the geometrical features and inherent behavior.

In the mathematical modeling process, three general assumptions have been made; (1.) that no failure occurs: i.e. the system absorbs and/or dissipates ALL the impact energy (within the design range) without damage to the constituent components, AND maintains its intact profile after the impacts). (2.) The spheres are to be in uniform contact with each other *before* and *after* loading cycles. (3.) Energy dissipation through heat and sound is considered to be minimal. (4.) Minimal pre-stretch of the membrane before and after loading.

The Skin

Main modes of energy absorption visualized for this component are: (a) Energy as a result of elastic compression of the component's wall, localized at the area of impact contact surfaces; E_1 , (b) Energy attributable to shear stresses; E_2 , and (c) Energy due to elastic deflection, localized around the impact incidence region; E_3 .

Figure 3: Fascia cross-section

(i) Energy due to elastic wall compression, E_1

In the context of an automotive bumper system, Figure 3 shows a typical general transverse cross-section of a fascia (or *Skin*). By virtue of the cross-sectional thickness t being too small, the energy absorbed by way of localized elastic compression of the material, E_1 , may be considered negligible and has consequently been neglected.

(ii) Shear stresses energy, E_2

At the point of impact incidence, the impact load will induce transverse shear stresses τ_{xy} and τ_{xz} in the section due to the nature of loading. This is in addition to the normal stress,

σ_x due to flexure. Assuming the load acts through the shear centre, no shear stress τ_{xy} and τ_{xz} due to torsion are in play. From the general cross-sectional profile shown in Figure 3, the shear centre [2] is considered to be at a distance e from O where:

$$e = \left\{ \frac{12 + 6\pi \frac{b+b_1}{R} + 6\left(\frac{b}{R}\right)^2 + 12\frac{b}{R}\frac{b_1}{R} + 3\pi\left(\frac{b_1}{R}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{b_1}{R}\right)^2\frac{b}{R}}{3\pi + 12\frac{b+b_1}{R} + 4\left(\frac{b_1}{R}\right)^2\left(3 + \frac{b_1}{R}\right)} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Visibly from this equation, one can particularize this to the more familiar sections by varying b and b_1 or even putting them to zero. Energy absorption attributable to global bending moments has consequently been considered to be negligible as compared to the localized elastic strain energy at this zone. As such, the conventional two-dimensional deformation theory has been rendered inadequate. Instead, a non-linear model developed by David J. Steigmann [3, 4] has been adopted, estimating the energy of a thin body generated in response to a given kinematically possible three-dimensional deformation.

(iii) Elastic strain energy, E_3

Based on the localized nature of deformation conceptualized at this zone, the Euler equations for the estimate of strain energy have been deemed applicable. The total strain energy, E_3 , may be given by adapting Steigmann's equation [4] as;

$$E_3 = \int_k U(\vec{F}(x))dV = E + O(\varepsilon^5), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } E = \int_{\Omega} W(d, g, h, F, D, G)dA \quad (4)$$

$$\text{in which } W = \varepsilon U(F + d \otimes k) + \frac{1}{24} \varepsilon^3 \left\{ P(F + d \otimes k) \cdot (G + h \otimes k) + M(F + d \otimes k)[D + g \otimes k] \cdot (D + g \otimes k) \right\} \quad (5)$$

is the strain energy through order $O(\varepsilon^4)$ per unit area of Ω , $r(u) (= \hat{y}_0)$ is the map from the plate mid-surface Ω to its deformed image, ω , and $d(u)$, $g(u)$, $h(u)$ are *director* fields defined on Ω . These are the coefficient vectors in the expansion;

$$\hat{y}(u, \zeta) = r(u) + \zeta d(u) + \frac{1}{2} \zeta^2 g(u) + \frac{1}{6} \zeta^3 h(u) + O(\zeta^4), \quad (6)$$

and $F = \nabla r$ maps Ω' to the tangent plane $T_{\omega(u)}$ of the deformed mid-surface ω at point $r(u)$

Thin Encapsulating Membrane

(i) Localized Elastic Compression; E_4

Rubber and other elastomeric materials are basically cellular in structure, allowing a certain percentage of set under compression. As envisaged here-in, this energy absorption mode applies to membrane impact points that are tangentially sandwiched between

peripheral encapsulated granules and the skin's biasing hemispheres. By virtue of the contemplated membrane thickness ($\pm 1\text{mm}$) and impact surface area, energy so absorbed has been considered negligible, and hence neglected. Since there is no significant relative motion between the membrane and surfaces around it during impact, energy dissipation through friction has also been deemed negligible and similarly ignored.

(ii) Elastic Membrane Stretching

(a) Global stretching; E_5

In the context of an automotive bumper system, transverse (z – axis) deformation has conceptually been constrained to minimal, in order to maximize *free* granular media flow in the x (longitudinal) and y (axis of incidence) directions. Since the encapsulated granular content is not a continuum solid, and stretch effect is differential, stretching of the membrane will tend to be localized at the region of impact incidence, as well as at the two free extreme ends of the capsule along longitudinal axis. Degree of stretch will, however, be maximum at the point of impact incidence as the impacting object seeks to displace a bulk granular volume equivalent to its volume. For modeling purposes, the impact loading is assumed to be below some critical value that would cause membrane failure by rupturing / tearing off, taking thermal-effects into consideration and other working environmental conditions.

To model the stretch effect, an axisymmetric deformation of a circular membrane by a smooth sphere as illustrated by Kuo Kang Liu and Bing Feng Ju [5] has been adopted – see Figure 4 below;

Figure 4: Sketch of membrane deformed by a sphere.

They contended that, when a central load ω is applied to a film, which has elastic modulus E , undeformed radius a , and thickness h , via a sphere of radius R , a displacement δ will correspondingly occur at the pole [5]. The membrane was assumed to be an isotropic 3D

incompressible (rubber-like) material exercising a Mooney-Rivlin constitutive behavior. For such a material, the strain-energy function, W , was accordingly given as:

$$W = C_1 (I - 3) + C_2 (II - 3) = C_1 [(I - 3) + \alpha (II - 3)] \quad (7)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the material constants with the dimensions of stress, C_1 is equal to $E/6$; $\alpha = C_1/C_2$ and its value was given as 0.1 in their study. The parameters I and II are the strain invariants which may be expressed in terms of the principal stretch ratios, λ_1 and λ_2 , as $I = \lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_1^{-2} \lambda_2^{-2}$ and $II = \lambda_1^{-2} + \lambda_2^{-2} + \lambda_1^2 \lambda_2^2$.

Numerical solutions of the governing equations give the relationship between the force applied to the membrane and its corresponding deformation [5]. They gave their result in terms of dimensionless load Y and deformation X , respectively, as:

$$Y = \frac{6\varpi}{E h R} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and} \quad X = \frac{\delta}{R} \quad (9)$$

For membrane of $a/R = 5.0$ and without pre-stretch, Y can be given as a function of X [5]

$$Y = 0.78 X + 0.075 X^2 \quad (0 \leq X \leq 1.7). \quad (10)$$

In this equation, the parameter X is calculated based on the measured central displacement δ normalized by R . The profile of the deformed membrane can be computed and expressed in terms of the distance ρ and displacement δ from the central axis to a specific point at membrane.

Since the granules are incompressible and assumed to be in uniform contact, displaced granular volume at impact incidence region approximately equals the granular volume stretching the membrane axially at the free ends. As such, arithmetic sum of strain energy at both longitudinal ends equals the strain energy at impact incidence region. Using W as obtained from Eqn. (7), total strain energy may thus be approximated as:

$$E_5 = 2W \quad (11)$$

(b) Localized Stretching; E_6

At the impact interface, encapsulated granules at the peripheral tend to lock into receptive spaces created by the biasing hemispheres lining the interior walls of skin and base plate. Assuming little or no sliding between hemispheres and membrane, the peripheral granules individually stretch the membrane locally. Summatively, the strain energy so absorbed may be approximated as:

$$E_6 = 2nW_g \quad (12)$$

where W_g is the strain energy per locked granule within the impact incidence surface area A , and n is the number of the so locked spheres (granules). Equation (7) applies equally in

determination of W_g . Coefficient of 2 serves to accommodate the reflective effect of skin and base plate hemispheres. Area A depends on shape of impactor surface, and the relationship between A and n varies from one lattice structure to another, e.g. for BCC,

$$n = \frac{3}{16} \cdot \frac{A}{r^2} \quad (13)$$

where r is the radius of granules.

Granular Media Layer

Figure 5: Solid / Hollow / Soft-core Spheres

Sample sphere and inherent relations for a 10mm diameter are illustrated in Figure 5. The possible energy absorption and/or dissipation modes for this section of the assembly are (1.) normal forces perpendicular to contact plane, through virtual lattice geometry; E_7 , (2.) static and sliding friction parallel to the contact plane; E_8 , and (3.) global linear displacement; E_9 , as a result of collapse of unit local lattice structures and granular fluid flow at the interior of the capsule. However, these phases are interdependent, characterizing discrete granular transitional dynamics synonymous to that of an incompressible fluid.

At this zone, it is hereby contended that the impact force engages the encapsulated spheres at three inter-dependent phases. {1.} the biasing hemispheres lock the peripheral spheres in the capsule into lattice structural arrangement by default. This process is consequential to the so called ‘geometric frustration’ [6] typically known to characterize hard-sphere systems. This kind of frustration is generated by the steric constraints imposed by the hard-core repulsion of neighboring grains and the subsequent interlocking which leads to non-local cooperative macroscopic re-arrangement. {2.} as far as possible, the lattice structures so formed will behave like a structural reinforcement grid beneath the elastomeric membrane. Energy will be absorbed elastically by way of normal forces at the points of contact of adjacent spheres along the line joining their centers. During this phase, no slipping is contemplated. {3.} As the impacting object seeks to displace a global volume of spheres equivalent to its own volume, the lattice structural dimensions will disintegrate, starting with the spheres furthest from the biasing hemispheres – apparently spheres at the central axis of the capsule. This disintegration will entail massive energy dissipation through slipping, instantaneous inversion of unit lattice structures, and initiation of rapid granular flow.

During the three phases, random collisions will be dominant and energy dissipation and / or absorption will be dependent on the nature of the collisions, which are on the other hand dependent on magnitude and rate of the incident impact. Despite every sphere being in constant contact with more than one other sphere (8 for BCC, 4 for FCC and 3 for Simple cubic lattice), the contact between any pair is typically representative of any other pair of contacts. However, not all of these contacts are load bearing, especially with reference to the normal component. The distribution of the impact force as shared amongst the impact bearing spheres (4 for BCC, 2 for FCC and 1 for Simple cubic), and the oblique angle of incidence varies from one lattice structure to another. The paired collision model has been adopted in analyzing the energy balance implications in this zone of the capsule.

In modeling oblique collisions of elastic spheres, Maw, Barber, and Fawcett [7] extended the Hertz theory of impact, and through numerical integrations of the forces involved during the collisions, established that three regimes exist in a typical impact. At *low angle* of incidence, the contact surfaces always include a central region where the particles stick, while at *high values of this angle*, slipping persists throughout the collision. At *intermediate angles*, the collision involves both sticking and slipping contacts. They showed that under suitable circumstances, elastic strain energy stored in the solid is recoverable, so the tangential velocity of the point of contact may be reversed.

On the basis that theories of rapid granular flows cannot realistically incorporate the details of the Maw, Barber, and Fawcett theory, and because real spheres are inelastic, Walton proposed a simplified impact model based on three constant coefficients [8]. The *first* characterized the incomplete restitution of the normal component of the relative velocity at the point of contact. The *second* arises in collisions that involve sliding. Here, the latter is assumed to be resisted by Coulomb friction, and the tangential and normal components of the impulse are related by the coefficient of friction. The *third* arises in collisions that return a fraction of the energy stored on elastic deformation of both surfaces to the component of the contact velocity tangent to the spheres. Here, Walton assumes for simplicity that these collisions do not involve sliding and treats the reversal of the tangential velocity at the contact point using a constant coefficient of tangential restitution.

Figure 6: Typical geometry of a binary collision projected on the collision plane as depicted by Foerster et al. The velocities are shown before the impact.

Figure 6 shows the adopted binary collision as depicted by Samuel F. Foester et al [9]. They experimentally calculated the velocities of the particles emerging from a collision from the balances of linear and angular momenta and from the relations prescribed by Walton's impact model. They showed that a simple model based on three constant coefficients (Coulomb friction, normal, and tangential restitution) captures the behavior of the impact over a wide range of incident angles. However, they differed with the model to the extent of demonstrating that the tangential coefficient is not a constant. They considered two colliding spheres of diameters σ_1 and σ_2 and masses m_1 and m_2 with centers located at r_1 and r_2 .

During the collision, sphere 2 exerts an impulse J onto sphere 1 [9]. Accordingly, the velocities before and after collision can be related by:

$$m_1(c_1' - c_1) = -m_2(c_2' - c_2) = J \quad (14)$$

and
$$\left(2 \frac{I_1}{\sigma_1}\right)(\omega_1' - \omega_1) = \left(2 \frac{I_2}{\sigma_2}\right)(\omega_2' - \omega_2) = -n \times J, \quad (15)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the translational velocities, ω_1 and ω_2 are the respective angular velocities prior to the collision, $I = m\sigma^2/10$ is the moment of inertia about the centre of a homogenous sphere, and $n \equiv (r_1 - r_2) / |r_1 - r_2|$ is a unit normal defined along the line joining the centers of the two spheres. The primes denote the corresponding post-collision velocities.

In order to determine the impulse, the relative velocity g of the point of contact was defined [9] as:

$$g = (c_1 - c_2) - \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{2}\omega_1 + \frac{\sigma_2}{2}\omega_2\right) \times n. \quad (16)$$

In the normal contact phase, Eqns. (14) and (15) have been used to relate the contact velocities before and after collision as [9]:

$$g' - g = \left(\frac{7}{2m^*}\right)J - \left(\frac{5}{2m^*}\right)n(J \cdot n), \quad (17)$$

where $m^* \equiv (m_1^{-1} + m_2^{-1})^{-1}$ is the reduced mass. The usual coefficient of restitution e characterizes the incomplete restitution of the normal of g [9],

$$n \cdot g' = -en \cdot g, \quad 0 \leq e \leq 1 \quad (18)$$

In the sliding phase, the tangential and normal components of the impulse are related by the coefficient of friction μ [9],

$$|n \times J| = \mu (n \cdot J), \quad \mu \geq 0 \quad (19)$$

Combining Equations (15), (16) and (17) provides an expression for the impulse in terms of the normal and tangential components of g [9],

$$J^1 = -m^*(1+e)(g \cdot n)n + \mu m^*(1+e) \times \cot \gamma [g - n(g \cdot n)], \quad (20)$$

where the superscript (1) denotes collisions that involve sliding as contemplated in phase {1.} and {3.}, and γ is the angle between g and n ,

$$\cot \gamma \equiv g \cdot n / |g \times n| \quad (21)$$

As γ increases, sliding is deemed to cease when

$$n \times g' = -\beta_0 n \times g, \quad (22)$$

or equivalently at a value γ_0 of the collision angle, such that

$$(1 + \beta_0) = -\frac{7}{2}(1+e)\mu \cot \gamma_0, \quad 0 \leq \beta_0 \leq 1 \quad (23)$$

where β_0 is the tangential coefficient of restitution [9].

In this simple model, collisions with $\gamma \geq \gamma_0$ were assumed not to involve sliding, in which case the impulse was found by combining Eqns. (17), (18), and (22),

$$J^2 = -m^*(1+e)(g \cdot n)n - \left(\frac{2m^*}{7}\right)(1 + \beta_0)[g - n(g \cdot n)], \quad (24)$$

Likewise in this expression, the superscript (2) denotes collisions that do not involve gross sliding, as contemplated in phase {2.}.

(i) Virtual Reinforcement Elastic Energy, E_7

Generally, impulsive energy dissipation implications for any of these three phases, E_{J_i} , may be expressed as:

$$E_{J_i} = \frac{1}{2} V J_i N_i \quad (25)$$

where V is the impact velocity onto the system, J_i is the impulse at phase i , and N_i is the average number of load bearing contact pairs for the particular lattice structure at phase i , and is dependent on the contact area of impacted surface, A , size of spheres (radius r), and depth of the impulse at that particular phase as determined along the axis of impact incidence. For simplicity, depth may be expressed in terms of equivalent number of granular layers.

By using the value of impulse J as given in Eqn. (24) for phase 2, E_7 work out to:

$$E_7 = E_{J_2} = \frac{1}{2} V J_2 N_2 \quad (26)$$

For instance, since only 4 out of 8 pairs of granules that form a unit BCC lattice are load bearing, the corresponding value of N_2 may be derived as:

$$N_2 = \frac{1}{2}n_2 \quad (27)$$

where n_2 is the number of granules active at phase 2. For BCC, n_2 may be determined as:

$$n_2 = \frac{3}{16} \cdot \frac{A}{r^2} \cdot d_2 \quad (28)$$

where A and r are as defined in Eqn. (13)*, and $d_2 = 6$ is the depth of impulse propagation through phase 2. It is worth noting that for two or more integrated layers of paired contacts, all pairs of contact become load bearing and as such, $n_2 = N_2$.

Value of d_2 is determined from the impulse wave propagation as modeled in Chapter 5 i.e. estimating the layer at which the impulse wave tends toward zero. The general equations were given as:

$$J'_{\theta n} = \frac{1}{4} J'_v (\alpha^{n-1} \text{Cos } \theta) \quad (29)$$

$$\text{and } J'_{vn} = \frac{1}{4} J'_v \left(\alpha^{n-1} \text{Cos}^2 \theta + \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^{n-2} \text{Sin}^2 \theta \right) , \quad (30)$$

where $J_{\theta n}$ and J_{vn} denotes corresponding dispersive and vertical impulses at n^{th} granular layer, α is the dissipative impulse transfer factor for the paired contacts; θ is the angle between J_v and J_θ ; Since these equations are independent of radius of the granules, size does not count. Angle θ is a constant for any particular lattice structure and J is independent of the dissipative mechanisms of the system. This leaves α as the only determinant factor of the dissipative behaviour thus determined at phase 2.

(ii) Paired Contacts: Sliding / Spinning / Frictional Dissipation, E_8

Using the value of impulse J as given by Eqn. (20), energy dissipated at phase 1 and 3 may be determined as:

$$E_8 = E_{J_1} + E_{J_3} = \frac{1}{2} V J [N_1 + N_3] \quad (31)$$

where, for simplicity purposes $N_1 \approx N_3 = 8(d-1)$ for BCC.

(iii) Energy dissipation due to granular shear flow, E_9

Granules in this section of the capsule may be analyzed from a hydrostatic perspective. Analysis of factors that configure granular flow may hereby be broadly categorized into at least three clusters of properties: (1) Inelastic-Vs-Elastic particles, (2) Smooth-Vs-Frictional particles, and (3) Homogenous-Vs-Heterogeneous particulate composition. Other equally important aspects of granular media are the geometry of individual particles (determines the granular packing in space), the hydrostatic pressure and boundary conditions; the nature of confinement.

In context of the granular capsule within the conceptual bumper assembly model, flow may be simplified to a uni-axial flow for analytical purposes. Argument here is that flow in the vertical and transverse directions will be negligible as compared to the longitudinal flow along the central X-axis. Since the flow will be a response to an impact, it will accordingly be instantaneous, possibly resulting in permanent dislocation of individual granules despite reform of the capsule to normal profile after withdrawal of the impact; thus a mode of energy dissipation.

Predictions for rapid granular flow are derived from kinetic theories that exploit analogies between the colliding particles and agitated molecules in a dense gas [10]. The theories produce a set of partial differential equations and boundary conditions. Due to the necessary simplification of cases for analytical solutions purposes, these differential equations are generally solved numerically by discretizing the flow domain and by employing numerical techniques that are robust enough to handle non-linearities in the system of equations. Success of theories in predicting practical flows is dependent upon an accurate experimental determination of the properties of individual impacts [10].

H.Xu et al [10] suggested that the principal difference between granular flows and dense gases is that kinetic energy is dissipated in collisions. They considered cases in which the collisional energy dissipation is small (as assumed in the model of the granular capsule). They reviewed the equations of the kinetic theory for the conservation of mass, momentum, fluctuation energy, and species concentration. They illustrated their solutions for shear flows in rectilinear or axisymmetric rectangular channels with or without a body force.

The conservation laws of mass, momentum, and fluctuation energy for a collisional granular flow of identical spheres of diameter σ have been derived as [10, 11]:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla (\rho u) = 0 \quad (32)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \rho u \cdot \nabla u = \nabla \cdot T + \rho f, \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{3}{2} \rho u \cdot \nabla T = -\nabla \cdot q + T : \nabla u - \gamma, \quad (34)$$

where $\rho = \rho_s v$ is the density of granular fluid, ρ_s is the material density of the spheres, $v = \frac{\pi n \sigma^3}{6}$ is the particle volume fraction, n is the number density of spheres, u is the mean velocity, T is the stress tensor, f is the body force per unit mass, $T \equiv \frac{1}{3} \langle C \cdot C \rangle$ is the granular temperature, C is the particle velocity relative to the mean flow, q is the flux of fluctuation energy, and γ is the volumetric collisional dissipation rate of kinetic energy.

The stress tensor has the same form as in ordinary fluids [10]:

$$\mathbf{T} = \left[-P + \left(\lambda - \frac{2}{3}\eta \right) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right] \mathbf{I} + \eta \left[(\nabla \mathbf{u}) + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T \right] \quad (35)$$

where P is the pressure, \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor, λ and η are the bulk and shear viscosity, respectively.

The flux of fluctuation energy satisfies Fourier's law [10]: -

$$\mathbf{q} = -k \nabla T \quad (\equiv E_g) \quad (36)$$

where k is the conductivity of fluctuation energy.

For flows of smooth, slightly inelastic, identical spheres, Jenkins and Rickman [11] derived constitutive relations for pressure, transport coefficients, and energy dissipation rate. To the lowest order of $1 - e$, where e is the coefficient of restitution for collisions between two flow spheres, their results are

$$P = 4 \rho F G T \quad , \quad (37)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{8}{3\sqrt{\pi}} \rho \sigma G T^{1/2} \quad , \quad (38)$$

$$\eta = \frac{8J}{5\sqrt{\pi}} \rho \sigma G T^{1/2} \quad , \quad (39)$$

$$k = \frac{4M}{\sqrt{\pi}} \rho \sigma G T^{1/2} \quad , \quad (40)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{24}{\sqrt{\pi}} (1 - e) \rho \frac{T^{3/2}}{\sigma} G \quad , \quad (41)$$

where $G = v g_0(v)$ and $g_0(v) = (2 - v) / [2(1 - v)^3]$ is the Carnahan and Starling [12] radial distribution function at contact for identical spheres. The functions F , J and M of v are

$$F = 1 + \frac{1}{4G} \quad , \quad (42)$$

$$J = 1 + \frac{\pi}{12} \left(1 + \frac{5}{8G} \right)^2 \quad , \quad (43)$$

and
$$M = 1 + \frac{9\pi}{32} \left(1 + \frac{5}{12G} \right)^2 \quad , \quad (44)$$

Jenkins and Chang [13] showed that these constitutive relations can be extended to nearly elastic, slightly frictional spheres. The expressions for pressure, viscosities and conductivity remain unchanged to the lowest order, while the additional dissipation of kinetic energy due to friction is taken into account by using an effective coefficient of

restitution e_{eff} that replaces e in (41). Following Walton's simple impact model [14] and the experimental verification of Foerster et al [7], Jenkins and Chang [13] distinguished sticking (or rolling) collisions characterized by a coefficient of tangential velocity restitution β_0 , and sliding collisions featuring a Coulomb friction coefficient μ that represents the ratio of the tangential and normal impulses in gross slip. For small $1 - e$ and small μ , they derived the coefficient of restitution

$$e_{eff} \equiv e - \frac{1}{2} a_1 + \frac{1}{2} a_2 \frac{b_1}{b_2}, \quad (45)$$

where
$$a_1 = \frac{\mu}{\mu_0} \left[\pi \mu_0 \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan \mu_0 \right) + \frac{2 \mu_0^2}{1 + \mu_0^2} \left(1 - 2 \frac{\mu}{\mu_0} \right) \right],$$

$$a_2 = \frac{5}{2} \frac{\mu}{\mu_0} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \mu_0 \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan \mu_0 \right) + \frac{\mu_0^2 - \mu_0^4}{(1 + \mu_0^2)^2} \right],$$

$$b_1 = \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_0} \right)^2 \frac{\mu_0^2}{1 + \mu_0^2}; \quad b_2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mu}{\mu_0} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \mu \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan \mu_0 \right) + \frac{\mu_0^2}{1 + \mu_0^2} \right]$$

and
$$\mu_0 \equiv \frac{7(1 + e)}{2(1 + \beta_0)} \mu \quad (46)$$

(iv) Boundary Conditions, E_{10}

Figure 7(i): Bumpy boundary – Cylinders as illustrated by Jenkin's et al.

Figure 7(ii): Bumpy boundary - Hemispheres

At the interface between the granular flow phase and the lattice structures, there will be some energy flux implications as the lattice granules resist, and / or disintegrate to join, the flow. At the extreme limit, all the lattice granules will have joined the flow and the hemispherical bumps on the fascia and basal plate will be resisting the granular flow. Conceptually, the velocity gradient from the boundary walls to the central axis of flow conforms to a laminar flow, just like in ordinary Newtonian fluids.

Boundary conditions for the stress and energy flux are derived by considering changes in momentum and fluctuation energy of the flowing particles in their collisional interactions

with the boundary [10]. In collisional granular flows, bumpy boundaries have long been regarded as a convenient way of imparting momentum and fluctuation energy to the flowing grains. Since all preceding calculations assumed that the relative mean “slip” velocity between the grains and the wall is small compared with the particle fluctuation velocity, Jenkins et al [11] extended these previous works to large slip. Accordingly, they calculated the wall stresses and fluctuation energy flux between a flow of smooth, inelastic spheres and a bumpy wall featuring half cylinders of diameter d and separated by s as illustrated in Figure 7(i) above [10]. In the context of the granular capsule, Figure 7(ii), hemispheres are a good approximation of half cylinders in a bi-axial flow field, with

$d = \sigma$. As such, the analysis for boundary conditions may be approximated to be representative of both models in either flow direction.

From geometrical considerations, Jenkins et al [15] applied their results at a distance $\frac{1}{2}(d + \sigma)$ away from the line of centers of the bumpy wall,

$$N^B = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e_w)\rho\chi T\left(1 + \frac{v^2 \sin^2 \theta}{3T}\right), \quad (47)$$

$$S^B = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e_w)\rho\chi T\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}\frac{v}{\sqrt{T}}(\theta \csc \theta - \cos \theta), \quad (48)$$

and

$$Q^B = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e_w)\rho\chi T^{\frac{3}{2}}\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}\left[(\theta \csc \theta - \cos \theta)\frac{v^2}{T} - \theta \csc \theta(1 - e_w)\right]. \quad (49)$$

where N and S are the normal and shear stresses at the boundary, respectively, the superscript B denotes smooth bumpy cylindrical boundaries, Q is the fluctuation energy flux through the boundary into the flow, and e_w is the coefficient of restitution for collisions between a flowing sphere and the half-cylinders, v is the slip velocity, ρ and T are evaluated at $\frac{1}{2}(d + \sigma)$ away from the wall, and $\theta \equiv \arcsin\left(\frac{d + s}{d + \sigma}\right)$ is a parameter

characterizing the bumpiness of the boundary. The factor χ accounts for the effects of excluded area and collisional shielding on the collision frequency between the spheres and the boundary. Although the exact value of χ is not known, solutions of the governing equations only require ratios of the shear stress or the energy flux to the normal stress, from which χ cancels out.

Assuming that the normal stress at a frictional, bumpy wall is the same as the normal stress at a frictionless bumpy wall, Xu [16] provided a stress ratio and a flux of fluctuation energy that are valid over a large range of dimensionless slip v / \sqrt{T} for a frictional, bumpy boundary to be approximately,

$$N = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e_w)\rho\chi T\left(1 + \frac{v^2 \sin^2 \theta}{3T}\right), \quad (50)$$

$$\frac{S}{N} = \left(\frac{S}{N}\right)^B + \left(\frac{S}{N}\right)^F \quad (51)$$

$$\text{and hence, } Q = Q^B + \Delta Q^F \equiv E_{10} \quad (52)$$

$$\text{where } \left(\frac{S}{N}\right)^B = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} (\theta \csc \theta - \cos \theta) \frac{\frac{v}{\sqrt{T}}}{1 + \frac{v^2}{3T} \sin^2 \theta}$$

is the contribution of the bumps to the shear stress, and

$$\left(\frac{S}{N}\right)^F = \min \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{14} (1 + \beta_{0w}) \frac{v_{rel}}{\sqrt{T}}, \mu_w \right)$$

is the frictional contribution. Q^B is given by (49) and

$$\Delta Q^F = \min \left(\begin{array}{l} NT^{1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \left[7\mu_w^2 - \frac{\pi}{2} \mu_w \left(1 - \frac{v_{rel}^2}{3T} \right) \right] \\ NT^{1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{7}{3} \mu_w^2 \end{array} \right) \quad (53)$$

is the contribution to the energy flux due to friction only.

Base Plate: Bending moments, shear, compressive stress energy

Further assumptions made here include (1.) that negligible shear loading exists between the flat plate and the attached biasing hemispheres, and (2.) that the layer is expected to function strictly within its elastic limits, which are meant to be below or equal to those of the motor-vehicle structural panels. Its behavior may thus be generalized to that of a slender beam, whereby external work done by the impact force may be equated to the internal strain energy attributable to both bending and transverse shear stresses.

Figure 8: Component D with biasing hemispheres

For a simply supported three point bending member of constant cross-section, the elastic strain energy due to bending, U_b , is given by [17];

$$U_b = \frac{P^2 L^3}{96EI} \quad (54)$$

where P is the load at a given point on the load deflection curve, L is the support span of the beam, E is the material's modulus of elasticity, and I the first moment of the cross-sectional area. For more precise results, this latter value may be moderated to account for the effect of hemispheres attached to the slender beam, thereby replacing I with a derived effective moment of area, I_{eff} . The corresponding deflection, Δ_B , at the mid-point of the support span, may be determined by an energy method as;

$$\Delta_B = \frac{PL^3}{48EI} \quad (55)$$

where $I_{zz} = bh^3/12$ for a rectangular cross-section with thickness h , and breadth b .

For the same loading set-up, the elastic strain energy due to transverse shear stress, U_τ , is given by [17];

$$U_\tau = \frac{fP^2 Lh^2}{96GI} \quad (56)$$

where f is a form factor, equal to 1.2 for a rectangular cross-section. For most metals, $G \approx 0.4 E$ and it has been found that [17];

$$U_\tau = U_b \left(\frac{3h^2}{L^2} \right) \quad (57)$$

and for slender beams; $L/h = 10$, $U_\tau = 0.03U_b$ which may be neglected. Since the deformation of this member is limited to the allowable deflection of the automotive panels to which it will be attached, the insignificance of U_τ has been imposed. By virtue of the component being thin, the elastic strain energy absorbed through localized elastic compression has as well been considered negligible and hence neglected.

For generality with respect to constituent material diversity, we may combine Eqns. (54) and (57), to obtain:

$$E_{11} = U_b + U_\tau = \frac{P^2 L^3}{96I} \left[\frac{1}{E} + \frac{f}{G} \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \right] \quad (58)$$

For the conceptual automotive bumper system, the energy absorbed and dissipated according to Eqn. (1) may now be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{E}_T = \mathbf{E}_3 + \mathbf{E}_5 + \mathbf{E}_6 + \mathbf{E}_7 + \mathbf{E}_8 + \mathbf{E}_9 + \mathbf{E}_{10} + \mathbf{E}_{11} \quad (59)$$

where the respective values of \mathbf{E}_i are as given by Eqns. (3), (11), (12), (26), (31), (36), (52) and (58) respectively.

Conclusions

Of the eight components in equation (59), some modes are absorptive while others are dissipative. Calculations based on experimental data and dimensions indicated that a greater percentage of the incident impact energy is dissipated, the rest being absorbed to be released after the impacting load is taken off. Bearing in mind that the system regains its dimensional portfolio after unloading, this results represent a potential breakthrough into non-destructive impact energy management. Further works need be done in order to optimize the system. This may be complemented by optimal selection of materials and dimensional analysis, preferably in conjunction with discrete element simulation analysis.

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